

Sonifying an Office Gadget to Indicate Air Quality

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ABSTRACT

Poor indoor air quality can produce headaches, fatigue, as well as respiratory and vision issues. Sonification might provide a way to increase people's awareness of their surrounding's air quality and activate preventive actions. In this paper we present the prototype of a sonically augmented interactive office gadget that provides information about air quality when a person interacts with it. We report the results of a user study comparing four sonification models (Abstract, Musical, Concrete and Cultural Models). Results show that the Abstract, Musical and Concrete models are equally effective in displaying air quality levels, while the Cultural model performs less well. Additionally, the Concrete and Musical models are preferred over the Abstract and Cultural models as their sonic qualities are considered more appropriate for what they aim to represent. As a result of this study, we aim to further develop the Musical and Concrete models as well as a Hybrid Model that combines the main characteristics of both.

1. INTRODUCTION

Within workspaces and on desks it is not uncommon to find a number of items that personalise the space. These items could be photographs, plants, trinkets, art to name a few [1]. It has been found that being able to personalise one's own work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction and well-being. Employee well-being is associated with higher morale, lower absenteeism, and higher productivity [1]. Office gadgets are one type of possible objects which are commonly found in office environments. Examples are: the drinking bird, as described by Frank in [2] or the Newton's Cradle, as described by Gavenda and Edgington in [3].

An investigation on how these objects might enhance the cognitive states of an individual can be found described by Karlesky and Isbister in [4]. This research was further developed in [5] where it was found that fidgeting and fiddling with items around one's own workstation are linked to self-creativity, focus and calm.

The amount of CO₂ in offices and indoor spaces has been shown to be associated with symptoms such as fatigue, headaches, respiratory and vision problems [6]. An office gadget that sonically indicates to the user the CO₂ levels

Figure 1. Hourglass augmented to sonify the air quality within an office environment. Photoresistors can be seen attached to the chambers, Arduino and breadboard are attached to the side, with the CO₂ monitor and accelerometer on the breadboard.

within their workspace area has obvious benefits for their health and well being.

This paper reports on a project that is part of a wider study into the sonification of air quality. In this project we have augmented an office gadget, a hourglass, with sound in order to communicate the current state of air quality in the room, namely the CO₂ level (Fig. 1). Sound models and their ability to communicate the air quality are then examined.

2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Extensive research exists into the negative effects of CO₂ in working environments [6–9]. The levels of CO₂ in a working space appears to be closely related to a phenomenon called *sick building syndrome* (SBS). CO₂ levels greater than 800 parts per million (ppm) were found to be linked to an increase in SBS within the office [10]. The main symptoms found were eye irritation and upper

respiratory symptoms. In offices the major contributor to increasing CO₂ levels are the occupants, with CO₂ being added to the environments when people exhale [11]. CO₂ is believed to be an indicator of air pollutants, rather than the direct cause of the observed symptoms [11]. Well ventilated spaces can counteract the effects associated with high CO₂ levels [12]. The same study recommended that the CO₂ levels be maintained below 1500 ppm, while [13] noted that exposure to 1000 ppm and above can affect cognitive performance.

Art works or objects in a room have previously been used to provide information about the air quality in the environment. An example is the interactive art display of CO₂ room levels described by Polli in [14]. The display included a robotic rover which drew a line on the wall relating to the CO₂ level in the space. It drew a horizon of “tall and short grasses” illustrating the changing CO₂ levels over time. The purpose of this artwork was to promote activism and social interactions. However the paper does not provide strong evidence that these goals were achieved.

Instead of displaying data in a visual manner it can be represented aurally through sonification, defined as “*the use of non-speech audio to convey information. More specifically, sonification is the transformation of data relations into perceived relations in an acoustic signal for the purposes of facilitating communication or interpretation.*” [15]. The sonification of data within a shared office environment was reviewed by Vickers in [16]. Here sonification was described as a form of “*serendipitous monitoring*” where attention is focused on a primary task (normal office work) whilst the data is monitored indirectly. A further study by Hermann et. al. [17], highlighted the benefits of this type of sonification compared to traditional alarms and warnings that only become active once a critical threshold has been reached. Sonification might help individuals to indirectly monitor air pollution and take preventative action prior to any such critical levels being reached.

An example of sonification of air pollution was shown by Hall et. al. in [18] where bicycles are augmented with speakers, GPS tracker, an air pollution sensor and a raspberry pi, enabling them to generate audio. The bicycles were presented at Lisboa Soa¹ an environmental sound art festival. Participants were invited to cycle around the city and the data obtained was logged. Researchers were able to build up an air pollution map of the city, while participants were able to perceive through sound the air pollution levels at their current location. Sounds used for the sonifications included the sound of fog horns as well as the sound of panting and gasping. A similar project was presented by Arango et. al. in [19] and [20] where a coat was augmented with air pollution sensors allowing the user to measure the air pollution at their location. Sound pulses (not further described) communicate data by varying their speed and pitch.

A sonification of NO₂² and O₃³ concentration was presented in [21], using filtered noise, sawtooth oscillators and square oscillators. The authors found that untrained listen-

ers could identify air pollution data trends through sonification. The paper identified the need for further work in relation to seasonal trends and geographical positioning.

Three portable devices that could communicate CO₂ levels sonically, visually and haptically respectively were presented by Hogan and Hornecker in [22]. The auditory feedback was mapped to the pitch of a synthesised sound, (details of the type of sound are not given). Results showed that subtle changes in CO₂ levels were difficult to comprehend from their air pollution data sonification, but all the devices stimulated social engagement about air quality and ventilation.

This project follows on from previous examples of sonification of air quality data but specifically focuses on CO₂ levels within an office environment. This research brings together the theme of office space personalisation, which promotes office well-being [1], while allowing users to serendipitously monitor the air quality at their workspace. Such an augmented office gadget may assist with increasing morale and productivity, encouraging a sense of calm but also allowing the user to monitor air pollution and take preventative measures [17], avoiding potential symptoms like fatigue and respiratory issues [6].

Unlike previous research, we focus on determining if users are able to identify levels of air pollution through different sonification mappings of CO₂ levels. Further to this, we examine how clearly the sounds represent the air quality data as well as which sounds are preferable. Four different sound models were used, each with their own mappings. Results will then be able to inform future sonifications of air quality data within an office environment.

3. DESIGN

In this project we aimed to augment an office gadget with sound and an air pollution sensor. We investigated a number of office devices that could be easily prototyped and augmented with sound. We looked for objects that one might interact with at times, such as the Newton’s cradle, with the aim of augmenting with sound both the normal object behaviour and the data coming from a CO₂ sensor attached to it. For our prototype, an hourglass was chosen as a very well understood and common object, that could be easily built with accuracy. A photo of the augmented hourglass is shown in Fig. 1. The object is based on a tutorial given in [23]. The prototype is made using recycled plastic and wood, with salt being used as the grains within the chamber.

3.1 Electronics Components

An Arduino Uno was used to receive data from sensors and communicate with a laptop. Four sensors were used to monitor the state of the object. An Adafruit CCS811 air quality sensor was used to monitor the CO₂ level in the space. Two photo-resistors were attached to the upper and lower cavities, indicating when the reservoir of grains had expired. An ADXL377 accelerometer was used to determine when the hourglass was turned.

¹ www.lisboasoa.com

² NO₂ - Nitrogen Dioxide

³ O₃ - Trioxigen or Ozone

3.2 Sonic Outputs

Sounds were produced on a laptop using Pure Data (vanilla 0.50), with communication from the arduino using the comport object and an additional patch which extracts serial print data [24]. The four sound models - referred to as Abstract, Musical, Concrete and Cultural - were developed along different criteria. The sounds were only audible while the salt was pouring from the top to the bottom chamber. Photo-resistors detected the beginning and end of the flow. This allowed the user to identify when the salt grains had finished falling, giving them the option to interact and turn the hourglass again or not.

Abstract Model: This is a pulsating FM synthesiser model, inspired by an example from Puckette [25]. It was created so that the air quality data linked to the magnitude and frequency of the pulse while the modulation index was controlled by an LFO. When the air quality level is good, the pulsation is approximately 50 - 60 beats per minute, which represents low activity. When the measured air quality decreases the pulse rate and depth increases, designed to give the perception of more activity and effort.

A second FM model was linked to the time taken for the grains to fall from the top chamber to the bottom. The fundamental frequency increases over the time the grains fall with a random variable added making this increase have a meandering quality. The modulation index and frequency are randomised between 15 and 2 times the carrier frequency.

Musical Model: This was created using a bell tone based on an algorithm by Jean-Claude Risset [26]. Historically bells have been used to communicate information (e.g. the sound of the church bells) and alarms. In our model the increase in air pollution equates an increase in the tempo of the bells. The fundamental frequencies of separate drone type tones increases as the grains build up in the bottom chamber.

Concrete Model: This model was developed based on the sound of wind blowing through wires and trees with the assumption that the sound of wind could be easily connected to the idea of air. This model is based on Farnell's wind [27]. The centre frequency of the bandpass filter on a 'wind howling around a wire' sound effect model adjusts with the CO2 level. The wind speed and level of gusts also adjusts with CO2 levels. A separate wire model [27], was linked to the falling of the grains between the chambers. The centre frequency of the bandpass filter used in the model decreases as the grains fall from the top to bottom.

Cultural Model: The CO2 level is connected to a number of frog sound effect models by Andy Farnell [27]. Although triggered randomly, the number of 'croaks' is directly related to CO2 levels. This model was based around a popular saying that describes a hoarse voice as having - 'a frog in the throat'. The frog croak sound can also be easily associated with someone coughing. Farnell's 'fan' model [27] was adapted so that the speed of the fan decreased as the grains fell from the top to bottom. A demo video⁴ shows the hourglass components and sonification.

⁴ <https://youtu.be/aNTzjXqb5Js>

Instance	CO2 level	Comments
Excellent	400	This background level of CO2 is not problematic [11]
Good	415	This level of CO2, a slight increase on the background level of 400PPM, was chosen to signal the start of a deterioration of air quality [11]
Poor	1000	This value was chosen as it was found in [13] that prolonged exposure to CO2 starting at this level affects cognitive performance

Table 1. Relationship between sound instances and CO2 level in PPM

4. METHOD

Research was carried out to investigate the effectiveness of the different sound models, specifically with respect to the clarity of the auditory display of air quality data. We additionally investigated which sound model was preferred by the subjects as the clearest sound model might not be necessarily the preferred. Identifying aspects of clarity and preference can then be used to inform future designs. A small user test was designed to evaluate the prototype and gather feedback about these aspects relating to the four sound models implemented thus far.

4.1 Participants

A total of eight participants (P1 – P8) took part in the test: three female and five males, aged between 23 and 48, with an average age of 31. When asked if participants had personal objects or gadgets on their work desk 6 participants (75%) stated that they did, although only 2 participants out of 6 listed personal items (small skull head, magnetic toys) rather than generic electronics (speakers, tablets, etc). All participants stated that they had some form of musical or sound education. This varied from high school level to PhD in sound and music computing level. Tests were carried out in an office room within KTH Royal Institute of Technology.

4.2 Test Design

For each sound model participants were presented with three different air quality instances: poor, good and excellent (see Table 1). The hourglass was active (grains flowing from top to bottom) when participants were presented with each instance.

A short introduction to the study was provided to all participants prior to the user test commencing. They were told that the hourglass was augmented with audio and that the sound would provide information about air quality in the room. Each of the four sound models were presented to the participants in a random order. For each sound model, three instances of air quality (see Table 1) were presented in a random order to participants. Participants were able to

listen to all the instances and ask for any to be repeated before indicating on a prepared form which air quality level (poor, good, excellent) they believed each sound represented. In total, 24 instances of each sound model were presented during the user test (each participant listened to three instances of each sound model).

Once participants had indicated which air quality the sound instances represented, they were invited to rate, from 1 (completely unclear) to 10 (completely clear), how clearly they thought the sound instances represented the three levels of air quality and their reason for this rating. This shows which of the models communicates the measured air quality best to our participants, and how clear they perceived this communication to be.

Additionally, after participants had heard the three sound instances, they were asked whether they could name one or more sound characteristic that changed as the grains fell from the top to the bottom chamber. Identifying the sound changes over the time of the falling grains gives an indication as to whether the sonic representation of said falling grains was perceived or not. Furthermore, participants were asked whether they could name one or more sound characteristic that they thought related to the air quality to see if they could identify a specific sonic component or if the perceived air quality level was based on a general appreciation of the overall sounds. Finally, after hearing all four sound models, participants were asked to rank the sound models in order of preference, and comment of the reasons of their choices as they may prefer a certain sound even though it is not as clear as another. Any additional comments were noted at the conclusion of the user test.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Abstract Model

For the Abstract model, 2 out of 24 instances were wrongly identified in terms of air quality level (see Fig. 2). P3 identified the good air quality sound instance as poor, and the excellent air quality sound instance as good. The mean rating for clarity for this model was 7.13 out of 10 with a standard deviation of 2.03. A boxplot of these results is shown in Fig. 3.

Amongst comments relating to the clarity rating, P2 stated *“The additional oscillating tones add a sense of urgency. More frequent = More urgent = poorer air quality”*. A total of three participants directly mentioned the frequency of oscillations indicating the change in air quality. P8 commented that *“The changes are clear, with a more subtle sound on the 3rd instance (Excellent)”*. P7 stated they struggled identifying the changes in air quality with this sound model stating that *“It is a bit hard to hear what is positive in these sounds. I can hear the change, but I’m having a bit of a hard time to map it to good or bad air quality”*.

Three out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the salt falling over time, 4 stated they couldn’t and 1 identified the wrong characteristics (see Fig. 4). When asked to describe the characteristics, the successful participants correctly identified the increase

Figure 2. Number of errors when identifying air quality from sound instances for each model

in frequency over time as related to the grains increase in the bottom chamber. P4 stated *“The height of the salt pile affected the higher pitched background noise”*, while P1 stated *“Maybe the glissando in background but I am not very sure about that, sometimes it seems a bit random”*.

Seven out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the air quality and 1 stated they couldn’t, (see Fig. 4). P3 described the frequency of the pulsating sound changing with air quality, P1 stating *“Pulse frequency”*. P4 associated the change in volume with the change in air quality - *“The volume of the pulsating sound”*, while P5 identified both the frequency and volume of the pulsating sound to air quality, *“The sound volume and repetition changes depending on air quality”*.

When ranked against the other models, the Abstract Model was placed in 3rd place by 6 of the participants and in 2nd place by 2 (see Fig. 5). Of those participants ranking this model in 3rd place some of the comments included: *“Very scary, felt like a horror-movie”* (P4), *“I like that the sound is quite subtle, but it is still a bit alarming”* (P8), *“a bit unsettling”* (P7) and *“Gives you a feeling of being watched, space like and mysterious”* (P6). A comment from P1, who ranked this model in 2nd place, was *“Nice background drone, actually I would put this and Sound Model 2 (Musical Model) both as first preference”*.

5.2 Musical Model

For the Musical Model, 2 out of 24 instances were wrongly identified in terms of air quality level (see Fig. 2). The errors from this model were from P3 and P6, both of whom identified the excellent air quality sound instance as good. The mean rating for clarity was 6.38 out of 10 with a standard deviation of 2.33. A boxplot of these results is shown in Fig. 3.

P2 commented that - *“The bell sound adds a level of urgency. As it gets more frequent, it can tell how much poorer the air quality is”*. P8 rated the clarity as 10, stating *“Change in the data was clearly represented in the instances. Increasing alerting”*. In contrast, P6 rated the model for clarity as 3, stating *“They all sounded like quite*

Figure 3. Boxplot showing clarity ratings of air quality sonifications for each model

Figure 4. Identification of sound to object mappings

bad air quality”.

Four out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the salt falling over time, 3 stated they couldn’t and 1 identified the wrong characteristics (see Fig. 4). When asked to describe the sound characteristics that changed as the grains fell, successful participants identified that the change with the constant drone sounds in the background, although only 1, P2, stated that the “Frequency of the constant sound” changed. The others could only identify that something changed with the background sound but did not specify in what manner it changed. P1 stated that “There is a bell sound each time the ‘salt mountain’ falls”, but they were mistaken.

Seven out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the air quality and 1 stated they couldn’t, (see Fig. 4). They all correctly identified that the air quality was related to the bell sound. Comments in relation to the bell sound included “Intervals between bell sound decreases (faster sounds) with decreasing in air quality. No (bell) sound for excellent air quality” (P5), and “Alarm bell warnings increasing in urgency” (P3). P1 stated “Rhythm of the bells, fundamental frequency of the drone”, correctly identifying that the rhythm of the bells changed in accordance to air quality, but mistakenly thinking that the fundamental frequency of the drones changed with the air quality. Similarly, P4 stated “The frequency of the bells and volume of background drone”, failing to identify that the volume of the background drones were

Figure 5. Participants preference of the sound models

changing with the falling sand and independent from the air quality level.

The Musical Model was ranked in 1st place by four participants, followed by 2nd place by another three, and 3rd place by one participant. This is shown in Fig. 5. Of those who rated this model in 1st place, comments included “Nice bells, sounds meditative” (P4) and “I’m partial to the bell sound. It seems fitting to communicate urgency. But maybe have the bell sound appear when it is really poor (air quality)” (P2). Comments from participants who ranked this model in 2nd place included “The bells provide a clear signal for changing quality, and I want them to stop” (P8), and “Calming but still alerting. Would be annoyed with the bells after a while” (P7).

5.3 Concrete Model

For the Concrete Model, 3 out of 24 instances were wrongly identified in terms of air quality level (see Fig. 2). The errors from this model were from P1, P3 and P6, all of whom identified the excellent air quality sound instance as good. The mean rating for clarity of this model was 7 out of 10 with a standard deviation of 2.07. A boxplot of these results is shown in Fig. 3.

Four participants stated that the change in volume allowed them to identify changes between the instances. P7 stated “Easy to spot a difference between the instances, and for me the increase volume represent a poorer air quality”, and likewise, P5 stated “The volume increases as the air quality reduces. Also feels like the speed is increasing as the quality gets worse”. Some possibility of confusion was noted in the participants comments: “If the changes are too slow, there’s a chance that some people wouldn’t be able to notice” (P2) and “Sound instance 3 (Poor) can either be good air quality, because it is windy, fresh air, or bad because in could be a fan” (P6).

Five out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the salt falling over time, 2 stated they couldn’t and 1 identified the wrong characteristics (see Fig. 4). The successful participants correctly identified the decrease in pitch of one of the howling sound as the grains fall - “Pitch goes down over time / with more salt” (P8). P7 identified the characteristic that changed over time, but not how it changed, “The high pitch sound,

not the white noise. It matched the salt in the hourglass well. If the hourglass could make a sound in would be that kind of whistle". P4 and P5 were not able to identify the characteristic that changed, stating "It sounds a little bit like the flow of salt affects the noise" and "Humming sound which might correspond to the flowing salt" respectively.

Six out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the air quality, 1 stated they couldn't and 1 identified the wrong characteristics (see Fig. 4). The most common characteristic identified with air quality was volume, or level, increasing as the air quality decreased. Examples of comments are: "The high pitched sound increased in volume when quality dropped" (P4), "The white noise increasing. White noise = wind = Air = increasing when bad air quality" (P7) and "Overall level, and the level (and perhaps frequency) of the middle whistling sound" (P2). P1 believed the bandwidth of a filter was being altered between sound instances which was not the case.

The Concrete Model was placed in 1st place by four participants, 2nd place by two participants, with the remaining participants ranking this sound model as 3rd and 4th (see Fig. 5). Comments from participants that ranked this model in 1st place include - "The quiet sound was nice, felt positive" (P6), "Sounds like wind and is quite subtle" (P8), and "This one I could see myself use in an office. The white noise + whistle is subtle but I would notice a change" (P7). P1 ranked this in 3rd place stating "The sound reminded of whistles and winds that become annoying after a while".

5.4 Cultural Model

For the Cultural Model, 10 out of 24 instances were wrongly identified in terms of air quality level (see Fig. 2). Only P5, P7 and P8 made no errors when presented with the different sound instances. P2, P3 and P6 identified all the sound instances as poor, while P1 identified the good air quality sound instance as poor and the excellent air quality sound instance as good. P4 identified the excellent air quality instance as poor and the poor air quality instance as excellent. The mean rating for clarity of this model was 4.88 out of 10, with a standard deviation of 1.96. A boxplot of these results is shown in Fig. 3.

Participants indicated that it was difficult to identify the difference between good and poor. For example, P5 stated "Instance 1 (Good) and instance 2 (Poor) might be confusing as compared to instance 3 (Excellent), and P4 stated "Hard to tell the difference between 1 (Poor) and 2 (Good)". A similar comment was given by P7 "Didn't notice much changes between instance 1 (Poor) and 2 (Good), and the overall soundscape felt a bit discomforting, making it hard to map 'good' or 'excellent' ". This feeling of discomfort was highlighted by a number of other participants - "The background noise makes all sounds feel bad" (P6), "The constant sound felt really unpleasant" (P2), and "The consistent low drone is a bit creepy / eerie, this suggests to me that in general something is wrong" (P1).

Three out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the salt falling over time, 4 stated

they couldn't and 1 identified the wrong characteristics (see Fig. 4). Out of these, only Participant 8 identified that there was a decrease in pitch of the constant sound as the grains fell. P5 and P7 both identified that the humming, background noise corresponded to the flow of grains, but did not specify in what way the sound characteristics changed.

Three out of 8 participants correctly identify sound characteristics changing with the air quality and 5 stated they couldn't (see Fig. 4). P4 and P5 identified the frequency of frog sounds related to the air quality. P4 correctly identified the frog sounds as relating to the air quality, but perceived an increase in these sounds as an increase in air quality.

The Cultural Model was placed in 4th place by all participants but one (see Fig. 4). P5 ranked this model in 2nd place but stated "Sound might be too distracting". Other comments were "less interesting (P1), "too annoying" (P2) and "less indicative" (P3). P6 and P7 expressed negative comments about the model stating "Felt very dark" (P6) and "Quite unsettling. Reminded me of a dark forest" (P7).

6. DISCUSSION

In terms of clarity, Abstract, Musical and Concrete models seem to perform equally well (see Fig. 2). Participants intuitively understand the meaning of the sonification mapping and some are even able to identify the sound characteristics linked to air quality and the salt pouring. The Cultural model performs between 3 and 5 times less well indicating that participants found identifying air quality levels from this model's sounds a greater challenge.

A number of reasons for the Cultural Model's poor clarity have been identified from participants comments. Firstly, the fan sound effect that slows down as the sand grains pour was found to be disturbing by participants. It was mistaken as "machinery" (P8), "buzzsaw" (P4) or "helicopter" (P2), none of which are associated with clean air. The triggering of the frog sound effect did not communicate the air quality clearly enough. The 'croaks' were triggered by a random number generator and the frequency used to trigger the generator was linked to the air quality. This had the effect that the generation of the croak sounds could be sporadic no matter what the air quality.

Finally, the combination of the frog sound and the fan sound was not perceived as pleasant, being described as "very dark" (P6) and "unsettling" (P7). Additionally, the frog sound could be interpreted in completely the opposite way it was intended as demonstrated by P4 who thought that more frogs equated to a cleaner, greener environment. Additionally, P4 interpreted that when the frog 'croaks' subsided, they were "dying from bad air". When explaining the models to all participants, at the end of the study, it also became apparent that none made the connection between the frog sound model and the saying 'Frog in your throat' despite the fact that a number of people were familiar with the saying. The frog sound effect was not associated with coughing either. We conclude that these factors combined produced the result that the Cultural Model

performed much worse than the other three.

The mappings of the Abstract, Musical and Concrete Models characteristics to air quality and the salt pouring seem to have been overall more intuitive and clear, despite the fact that many participants were not able to completely identify which sound characteristics were linked to the pouring salt grains or the air quality. This is not a significant issue as the sonification should work intuitively, without requiring from the user learning or have detailed knowledge of what is happening. What is of importance here is the fact that participants were able to discern the different instances of excellent, good and poor air qualities overall.

In terms of preference, the Musical and the Concrete Models are clear favorites (see Fig. 5) with the Abstract Model in third place, and the Cultural Model last on fourth place. A Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum Test shows that the Musical Model is significantly different ($p = 0.006$) than an average ranking (2.5) as is the Cultural Model ($p = 0.005$). Although the Abstract, Musical and Concrete Models all have high ratings for clarity, participants had more negative cultural associations with the FM sound (see comments such as (“*felt like a horror-movie*” (P4), “*a bit unsettling*” (P7), “*a feeling of being watched*” (P6))) which might be the reason why the Abstract Model ranked below the Musical and Concrete Models.

Contrary to the negative associations with the Abstract Model, the Musical Model and Concrete Model both had more positive associations. The bells were described as “*meditative*” (P4) and “*Calming but still alerting*” (P7) however some comments suggested that the bell sound might become tiresome over time - “*a clear signal for changing quality, and I want them to stop*” (P8).

Similar comments were made in relation to the Concrete Model, received remarks included - “*felt positive*” (P6), “*is quite subtle*” (P8) and “*This one I could see myself use in an office*” (P7). The Concrete Model also attracted some criticism with both P1 and P4 describing the model as “*annoying*”. P2 also highlighted that the higher whistling tone “*will be annoying for people with tinnitus*”, which is an aspect that should be considered in further prototypes.

7. CONCLUSION

We have described the design of a sonically augmented interactive office gadget that aims to provide information about the room air quality to its user. We evaluated four different sound models (Abstract, Musical, Concrete and Cultural Models) via a user study. Results showed that the Musical and Concrete models are both the clearest as displays of information and the preferred models sonically.

A number of additional aspects should be considered in future developments. On the physical object, it is believed that force sensitive resistors below the grains would provide a better measure of the flow of grains. A number of photo resistors were intended to be used in this initial prototype, but we found that their sensitivity to light in the environment made them difficult to program with any ac-

curacy (measurements varied depending on lighting in different office spaces and even time of day).

Different physical objects might work better with the different sound models. For example, the Abstract Model might gain a higher preference rating for some people if connected to a more futuristic or ‘dark’ object.

As a result of this study, three sound models will be brought forward to the next development stage of the augmented hourglass: the Musical Model, Concrete Model and a Hybrid Model combining Musical and Concrete characteristics. This Hybrid Model is inspired by a comment from P2 “*Personal preference: wind sound from model 3 (Concrete Model) plus bell sound from model 2 (Musical Model). The combination makes the sound similar to a common city soundscape*”.

Furthermore, it would be of great benefit to carry out a longitudinal user-study, observing participants use of the object over a more substantial period of time. This would give a greater understanding of how the sounds integrate into the office environment, and if annoyance can occur with an increased exposure.

Finally, a number of different environments could be tested (e.g. home, vehicles, elevators). For instance it is known that poor air quality in vehicles is linked to negative cognitive effects [28], therefore a similar augmented object for vehicles could have the potential to make a significant difference in these environments.

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